

OIL PIPELINE VANDALISM: IMPLICATIONS ON MULTINATIONAL OIL CORPORATIONS AND HOST COMMUNITIES IN THE NIGER-DELTA, NIGERIA

Nwosu Chinedu Everest, PhD

Department of Sociology

Taraba State University, Jalingo

** Corresponding author: everestinox @yahoo.com

Abstract

Multinational oil corporations operating in the Niger-Delta, Nigeria have encountered different challenges which include oil pipeline vandalism and this has adverse implications on the oil multinationals as well as the host communities. In the quest to actualize the phenomena under study, this paper sourced information through published books, journal articles and conference proceedings. The frustration aggression theory was adopted as the theory suitable to guide this work. The paper concludes that, despite various attempts put in place by the federal government and multinational oil corporations in Nigeria to create a peaceful atmosphere and cordial relationship between multinational oil corporations and their host communities' tension, agitation and crises in the form of pipeline vandalism still persists. The paper recommends among others that, multinational oil corporations should as a matter of necessity always showcase their corporate social responsibility and ensure that it gets directly to members of host communities diligently as this will help to put an end to oil pipeline vandalism in the Niger-Delta, Nigeria.

Keywords: Oil Pipeline, Vandalism, Multinational Oil Corporations, Host Communities, Niger-Delta, Nigeria
